

Reactions of Pd(II), Cu(II), Ni(II) with Phenylazo-Bis-Benzaldoxime

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Phenylazo-bis-benzaldoxime reacts with Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) to give coloured insoluble complexes. The metal-ligand ratio in these complexes has been determined to be 1 : 2. They were gravimetrically estimated with the reagent with an error not more than ± 0.5 per cent. Electronic spectral, magnetic and I. R. studies of the complexes were made.

ARYLAZO-bis-oximes are reported in literature as a group of compounds formed by coupling diazonium salts (1 mole) and aldoxime or ketoxime (2 moles), possessing hydroxytriazine skeleton $-N=N-N(OH)$ ^{1,2}. Hydroxytriazines have been elaborately studied as analytical reagents,³⁻⁸ but only a few arylazo-bis-oximes have been synthesized and evaluated for their complexing properties⁹⁻¹¹. In the present communication, phenylazo-bis-benzaldoxime is reported as a new gravimetric reagent for palladium, copper and nickel. Palladium and copper are quantitatively precipitated at pH 2.0-7.0 and 2.5-7.0 respectively. The reagent is highly specific for these cations at pH 3.0. These metals are separated from Co(II), Ni(II), Zn(II), Mn(II), Cd(II), Bi(III), Sb(III), As(III), Hg(II), Pb(II), Sn(IV), Be(II), Mg(II), Al(III), Cr(III), Fe(II), Fe(III), Ti(IV), Zr(IV), Ce(IV), Th(IV), UO₂(II), Pt(IV), Rh(IV), Ir(III), Ru(III), MoO₄²⁻, WO₄²⁻, PO₄³⁻, F⁻ and NO₃⁻. The precipitation of Fe(II), Fe(III), Ti(IV) and MoO₄²⁻ is completely masked with NaF or KF. The partial hydrolysis of Sn(IV) and Zr(IV) salts is prevented by adding NaF and that of Bi(III) and Sb(III) by washing the complexes with 1% sodium potassium tartrate containing 0.5 ml of conc. HCl per 100 ml. Nickel is quantitatively precipitated at pH 5.5 and is separated from Zn(II), Mn(II), Cd(II), Mg(II), As(III), Be(II), F⁻ and PO₄³⁻ which do not form any insoluble complex at this pH.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Cu(II) and Ni(II) were prepared by dissolving A. R. (B. D. H.) copper sulphate and nickel sulphate in distilled water respectively and that of Pd(II) by dissolving palladium chloride in conc. HCl (A. R.), diluting and estimating its palladium content with dimethylglyoxime. 1% solutions of foreign ions were prepared by dissolving their nitrates or acetates in distilled water.

The reagent phenylazo-bis-benzaldoxime was prepared by coupling benzene diazonium chloride (1 mole) with benzaldoxime (2 mole) in dilute sodium hydroxide solution keeping pH 10 and temperature 0°. The product was crystallised from ether into cream coloured leaflets, m. p. 183°; reported⁹ 185°. 1% solution of the reagent in 95% alcohol was used in all estimations.

Ellico LI 10 pH meter and Phillips PR 9500 conductivity bridge were used for pH and conductivity measurements. Magnetic measurements were carried out on Guoy's Balance and electronic spectral measurements on Bausch and Lomb-spectronic '20'. The molecular weights of the ligand and the chelates were determined cryoscopically using benzene.

Gravimetric procedure : Metal ion solutions containing 10-25 mg. of the metal were diluted to 150 ml and pH adjusted in between 2.5-3.0 in case of Pd(II) and Cu(II) and 5.0-5.5 in case of Ni(II) with the help of N-HCl and 10% sodium potassium tartrate solution. Precipitation was carried out at room temperature by adding 1% alcoholic solution of the reagent dropwise with constant stirring till complete precipitation. It was digested on a hot plate at 60°-70° for 30 min. filtered, washed 4 or 5 times with hot distilled water and dried to a constant weight at 115°-120°. The results were found to be within $\pm 0.4\%$ error. When foreign ions were present the procedure for estimation was modified as described earlier.

Conductometric titrations : The conductometric titrations of palladium chloride, copper sulphate and nickel sulphate against phenylazo-bis-benzaldoxime as titrant indicated that the mole ratio in which the metal and the ligand combine is 1 : 2 in each case.

Stability of complexes : The stability constants of these complexes as determined by Bjerrum's pH titration technique^{1,2} were found as follows :

Complex	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁ K ₂
Pd-complex	9.10	7.64	16.74
Cu-complex	8.09	6.74	14.83
Ni-complex	7.48	6.39	13.87

The stability order follows the Irving-William Rule.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the reagent, phenylazo-bis-benzaldoxime and its Pd(II), Cu(II) and Ni(II) complexes are given in Table 1.

TABLE I

Name of the compound	Colour	Mol. wt.		m. pt. °C	Elemental analysis				Magnetic moment B.M.	I. R. cm ⁻¹
		Calcd.	Found		Calcd Metal	N	Found Metal	N		
Phenylazo-bis-benzal- doxime	Cream	346	335	183	—	16.18	—	16.30	—	3170,1445
Pd-complex	Yellowish red	796	788	246	13.39	14.06	13.34	14.14	Diamagnetic	1440
Cu-complex	Yellowish red	753	738	192	8.43	14.86	8.47	15.01	1.78	1442
Ni-complex	Greenish Yellow	748	732	182	7.84	14.96	7.81	14.84	Diamagnetic	1440

Note :- The ligand and the complexes were recrystallised from acetone.

The ligand shows strong absorption band in infra-red spectra characteristic of (O-H) stretching at 3170 cm⁻¹. This band in free (-OH) appears at about 3600 cm⁻¹. Hydrogen bonding, however, shifts this band to lower frequency. This is true because (-OH) group in the reagent molecule is placed in a very close proximity of the polar unsymmetrically substituted azo (-N=N-) group. The disappearance of this band in the complexes points to the replacement of hydrogen from (-OH) group by the metal. A strong and sharp band at 1445 in the ligand molecule may be assigned to (-N=N-) group which is slightly lowered in the complexes.

(PdL₂): The yellowish red, diamagnetic Pd(II) complex is probably square planar which is the common stereochemistry for the palladium(II) complexes.

(CuL₂): This complex has a magnetic moment of 1.78 B. M. which is considerably lower than that of the tetragonally distorted octahedral or a tetrahedral Cu(II) complex¹³. The lower magnetic moment may be a result of the increased separation between the ground ²B_{1g} and the components of ²T_{2g} term of the energy level for Cu(II) ion with a square planar symmetry¹⁴. A broad band at ~560 nm in the visible spectra of the complex also points to the square-planar stereochemistry of the Cu-complex.

(NiL₂): This complex is found to be diamagnetic. The electronic spectrum of the complex exhibits two shoulders at ~410 and ~510 nm which points to its square-planar stereochemistry.

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